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GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ISSUES OF FOOD SECURITY AND URGENT TASKS

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Anotation. Food security is an issue of global importance. This article will analyze the main aspects of food security, global and national problems of food security, international cooperation and current tasks.

Annotatsiya. Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi - bu global ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan masala hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada oziq-ovqat xavfsizligining asosiy jihatlari, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligining global va milliy muammolari, xalqaro hamkorlik va dolzarb vazifalari tahlil qilinadi.

Аннотация Продовольственная безопасность-это вопрос глобального значения. В этой статье будут проанализированы основные аспекты безопасности пищевых продуктов, глобальные и национальные проблемы безопасности пищевых продуктов, международное сотрудничество и текущие задачи.

Key words: Food security, international cooperation, global, national issues, FAO, recent research, national products, agriculture.

Introduction: Food security means having the opportunity to consume food that is rich in essential elements and safe, ensuring a healthy lifestyle at any time. Therefore, it can be said that, in the current process of globalization, ensuring the provision of quality food products for the population of countries within the scope of purchasing ability has become a significant issue.

In our independent country, during the process of socio-economic development, the high results achieved are primarily due to the evolving content and essence of our economy, the correct choice of the path of independent development, and the thorough foundation of the economic policy strategies being implemented, with the selfless labor of our people serving as the main factor.

A number of decisions and regulations aimed at improving food security in our country have been adopted since the early days of independence. A clear example of this is the adoption of the 1997 Law on the Quality and Safety of Food Products. This law established the legal foundations for ensuring the population's access to quality and safe food products [1].

Looking at the January 16, 2018 decree of our President, "On further ensuring the country's food security," the essence of the decree is to fill the markets of our country with affordable, high-quality, and safe food, improving the trade opportunities of our people and creating healthy competition. Thus, the development and improvement of this sector is of great importance not only in material terms but also economically and socially in today's world [2].

Food Security: Global and National Issues As we all know, food product safety is a global, urgent, and national issue that countries around the world face. Despite the effective efforts being made in both developing and developed countries in the production of food products, the increase in

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food production has been lagging behind the growing population. This indicates that the problem is deepening in countries where there are insufficient conditions to develop the sector. Due to the increasing world population, economic problems, climate change, and several other factors, it is becoming increasingly difficult to meet the demand for food products on Earth. Based on data from the United Nations and the World Health Organization, it can be stated that over 840 million people globally, or one in every eight individuals, do not have enough food to eat. Recent studies show that more than 30% of the world's population suffers from a deficiency of essential micronutrients and vitamins, which are vital for the human body. In 52 countries around the world, serious and alarming levels of hunger have been recorded. As a result, over 160 million children worldwide are facing problems related to stunted growth and physical and personal development. Moreover, in the past three years, this indicator has been steadily increasing [3].

Along with ensuring food security in our country, we are also exporting agricultural products to the world, which contributes significantly to the food security of other countries. Our country is gaining high recognition in the global community. For instance, in 2015, our country was one of the 14 nations worldwide that received the special food security award from the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). This recognition demonstrates the proper assessment of our consistent policies in this field.

According to experts from the FAO, food security includes the following indicators: stability, food availability, access to food, and utilization. Therefore, ensuring full access to food products for people is considered part of the country's food security. Meeting the demand for basic food types for the population of our country, ensuring the price and quality of food, and guaranteeing its safety by the state are among the important conditions for economic and social development [4].

In this area, our country has been consistently implementing strategic and targeted measures to provide the population with quality food products and to cultivate them. More than twenty million tons of fruits, vegetables, and root crops are grown in our country, and in recent years, over 800,000 tons of food storage capacity has been achieved. However, this is currently insufficient to meet our needs. Therefore, if the storage of our produced products is increased by at least 10%, it will enable us to provide the population with food products at the same prices for years to come [3].

Conclusion Achieving food security in the country is directly related to the implementation of strategies and programs in agriculture, the food industry, and trade sectors. Therefore, it is necessary to further strengthen state support for these sectors and industries [3].

In conclusion, considering the increasing global food shortage, it is essential to effectively and qualitatively implement measures that will enable our country to meet domestic demand and reduce the demand for imported food products from foreign markets. Given the current complex political situation in the world, where countries involved in the global market are imposing sanctions on one another, it is crucial to make effective use of potential disruptions and interruptions in the circulation of goods and products in world markets. This would allow us to increase the export volume of national products grown in our country, which is in line with our goals. The additional revenue generated from these measures will not only create favorable conditions for the renewal and recovery of sectors in our economy that are facing setbacks, but it will also significantly contribute to the economic growth of our country [4].

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